

Basal Data Sheet

Patient study code:

Sex

Prescribed regimen:

Age

Comorbidities:

HTN:

DM :

if yes glycated:

History of HCC:

HCV RNA Negative

positive

Lab Values:

ALT:

AST:

WBCS:

HgB:

BIL:

Albumin:

S.Cr.:

AFP:

INR:

Platelets:

US:

Cirrhosis Negative

positive

MRI or Triphasic CT If applicable

Follow-up of treated patients Wk 12

Date : — / — / — Physician Name : — Patient ID : —
Issue no : — Centre ID : —

Clinical, Lab, FUP

HCV RNA Neg Pos Quant : — IU / ml Limit of det : —
ALT (IU/L) : — / — AST (IU/L) : — / — Total bilirubin (mg/dl) : —
WBCx10³/mm³ : — ANC X10³ / mm³ : — Hb (g/dl) : — Plateletsx 10³ / mm³ : —
PC : —% INR : — Albumin (g/dl) : —
Blood sample storage Yes* No * If Yes, specify the ID sample : —

Presence of side effects :

Hematological : anemia others, —
 Dermatological rash others, —
 Hepatic jaundice ascites encephalopathy hematemesis
 Others : —

TREATMENT

Decision to : Continue with the same treatment Stop treatment ⁽¹⁾
 Change RBV dose to : — mg

Additional specify, —

(1) If stop treatment, specify the reason why :

Serious adverse event* Too many adverse events Others, specify : —

* An adverse event is called "serious" if it requires admitting the patient to the hospital
(please fill the NCCVH SAE form on line (ask for URL if not obtained) .

Week 12 Viral load negative positive

SUR 12 sheet

Follow-up of treated patients Wk 24

Date: ___/___/___ Physician Name: _____ Patient ID: _____
Issue no.: _____ Centre ID: _____

Clinical, Lab FUP

HCV RNA Neg Pos Quant: _____ IU/ml Limit of det: _____
ALT (IU/L): _____ / _____ AST (IU/L): _____ / _____ Total bilirubin (mg/dl): _____
WBCx10³/mm³: _____ ANC X10³ / mm³: _____ Hb (g/dl): _____ Plateletsx 10³ / mm³: _____
PC: _____% INR: _____ Albumin (g/dl): _____
Blood sample storage Yes* No * If Yes, specify the ID sample: _____

Presence of side effects:

Hematological: anemia others, _____
 Dermatological rash others, _____
 Hepatic jaundice ascites encephalopathy hematemesis
 Others: _____

TREATMENT

Decision to: Continue with the same treatment Stop treatment ⁽¹⁾
 Change RBV dose to: _____ mg

Additional specify, _____

(1) If stop treatment, specify the reason why:

Serious adverse event* Too many adverse events Others, specify: _____

* An adverse event is called "serious" if it requires admitting the patient to the hospital
(please fill the NCCVH SAE form on file (ask for URL if not obtained)).

Week 24 Viral load negative positive